

PARAMETRIC STUDY OF SIMULATION PARAMETERS FOR MOLECULAR DYNAMICS MODELING OF REACTIVE CARBON GASES USING REAXFF

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1 Introduction

Carbon-based materials are ideal for structural aerospace components because of their high specific strength and high specific stiffness relative to traditional aerospace metallic materials. Reactive carbon-based gases are common in the synthesis of carbon-based materials. Various reactive gas processes occur in the production of carbon-based material constituents like nanotubes, amorphous carbon films, and even soot particles formed from combustion. Electron beam deposition [1], chemical vapor deposition [2, 3], pulsed arc discharge deposition [4], plasma deposition [5-8], pulsed laser deposition [9, 10], laser ablation, combustion [11, 12], and ion beam irradiation [13] are all processes that are used in the manufacture of carbon-based materials where the source of carbon is a reactive carbon-based gas. Because of the wide range of processing methods and conditions that can be used to fabricate carbon-based materials, their development can be time-consuming and expensive.

Molecular modeling can be used to greatly facilitate the development and design of carbon-based materials. Molecular models give detailed atomic information not easily obtained from physical samples, and they provide precise control over environmental variables in the simulation. Traditionally, researchers modeled atom-atom interactions using Molecular Dynamics (MD) with fixed-topology force fields where bonds are defined at the beginning of a simulation and remain fixed throughout the simulation. However, since bond dissociation and formation are critical steps in the formation of carbon-based materials from a reactive gas, a new generation of force fields, such as the recently-developed Reax Force Field [14] (ReaxFF), are required to simulate these material systems. The

ReaxFF has the capacity to model bond dissociation and formation in carbon-based materials.

In the ReaxFF, the potential energy is defined as a function of bond order with energy penalties for non-equilibrium configurations. Parameters for the ReaxFF functions are determined by first simulating reactions that are expected to occur in a system of interest using computationally demanding *ab initio* methods. ReaxFF parameters are then defined that minimize differences between the *ab initio* and ReaxFF potential energies. ReaxFF has been shown to accurately describe bond dissociation and formation for a variety of molecular systems and conditions including oxidation of hydrocarbons [15], catalytic formation of nanotubes [14, 16], shock waves in polymers [17], and many more carbon-based systems [18-26]. However, a variety of ReaxFF force-field parameter sets and simulation parameters have been reported in these studies and it is unclear what parameter sets and simulation conditions should be used for carbon-based reactive gases.

The objective of this study is to determine the modeling parameters necessary for the accurate simulation of carbon-based reactive gasses using the ReaxFF. A parametric study is performed by monitoring the response of six carbon-based reactive gas systems modeled using various simulation time steps, simulated temperatures, and ReaxFF parameter sets. A description of the ReaxFF is followed by a description of the parametric study modeling details. The results of the study indicate that there is a critical time step in which further decreases in the time step size result in identical simulation results. The results also indicate that the temperature and parameter set can have a significant effect on the simulation.

2 ReaxFF

The molecular potential energy defined by many traditional force fields is composed of contributions from bond stretching, bond-angle bending, dihedral torsion, van der Waals interactions, electrostatics, and hydrogen bonding. With traditional force fields these energy contributions are directly dependent on the distance between the interacting atoms. The ReaxFF also contains these energy contributions. However, in ReaxFF, these terms are dependent on the bond order, which decreases to zero as the distance between the atoms is increased. In addition to these typical contributions, the ReaxFF has several additional energy terms to describe additional atomic interactions. The ReaxFF includes energy terms for conjugated systems, angles with a double bond, lone pair electrons, over- and under-coordinated atoms, a special term for the C_2 molecule, and potentially other terms depending on the individual ReaxFF parameter sets.

The time step required to get accurate results with the ReaxFF may be quite different than time steps used with traditional force fields. The time step is highly dependent on the stiffest portion of the force gradient experienced by the atoms during MD simulations. In traditional force fields the stiffest molecular interactions are often harmonic, which results in a constant stiffness for all deformation magnitudes. With the ReaxFF however, because bonds can break and form, the force between interacting atoms is non-linear. In addition, for specific molecular systems, like all-carbon systems, the force gradient can be much steeper than those in traditional force fields. Because of these factors, the selection of a MD time step that results in accurate predictions is not straightforward. As an example, consider the energy-deformation and force-deformation curve of the bond in a C_2 molecule shown in Figure 1 for both the ReaxFF and a typical harmonic alkene carbon-carbon bond. It can be seen that the energy slope near the equilibrium bond distance is much greater for the ReaxFF compared to the typical harmonic potential. It also shows that as the bond in the C_2 molecule is stretched the slope of the ReaxFF force curve varies significantly away from the equilibrium distance, contrasted to the constant slope of the harmonic potential force curve. As a result, the maximum MD simulation time step size that is required for the ReaxFF is expected to be

much smaller than for a traditional force field containing a typical harmonic bond.

Fig. 1 Comparison of the potential energy and force gradient for the bond in a C_2 molecule between the ReaxFF and a generic harmonic potential with stiffness of 549.0 kcal/mol and equilibrium bond distance of 1.34 angstroms

With traditional force fields, once the system is near equilibrium the time step size can be verified by running a simulation in the micro-canonical ensemble. If the time step is too large the total energy of the system will not be conserved, typically increasing over the course of the simulation. In some simple cases this method can also be applied to the ReaxFF by temporarily modifying the parameter set to disable favorable reactions, causing the initial system to remain in equilibrium, acting like a fixed-topology force field. However this only verifies portions of the force gradient found in the initial system. Once the reaction is allowed to continue new bonds and molecules will form that have force gradients that are not sampled.

An alternative approach to verifying the time step size is to run simulations of identical systems under

identical conditions with different simulation time step sizes. There will be a critical time step in which the time step and all smaller time steps will result in the same response in the system. This approach has the advantage that it will sample all portions of the force gradient present at any time during the simulation.

3 Parametric Modeling Procedures

For this parametric study six different initial gas molecules were included. Three pure carbon systems were simulated; C, C₂, linear C₄; as well as three radical hydrocarbons; CH, C₂H₂ with both hydrogen atoms bonded to a single carbon atom, and C₄H₄ shown in Figure 2. These small radical carbon and hydrocarbon molecules are expected to be present in various reactive gas manufacturing processes, possibly for only very brief time intervals.

Fig. 2 Initial gas molecules simulated

Two ReaxFF parameter sets were used to model the reactions. The parameter set of Nielson et al. [14] (henceforth referred to as Nielson) was originally parameterized for reactions expected in nanotube formation and growth from transition metal atoms. This parameterization is well suited for small cyclic and acyclic carbon structures, graphite, various graphenes, various nanotubes, fullerenes, and hydrocarbon reactions. This parameter set is also well suited for reactions of carbon with single nickel, copper, and platinum atoms. The parameter set of Chenoweth et al. [4], henceforth referred to as Chenoweth, is parameterized for the reactions of small hydrocarbon molecules with oxygen.

Three different temperatures were modeled as part of the parametric study. The responses of the reactive gasses at 300K, 1,500K, and 3,000K were predicted. This temperature range was selected based on the range of temperatures that carbon-

based structures can be exposed to during typical synthesis and operating conditions. The Berendsen thermostat was used to maintain the temperature in the MD models with a damping coefficient of 5 fs.

Five different simulation time steps were selected: 0.4 fs, 0.2 fs, 0.1 fs, 0.05 fs, 0.025 fs. These time steps encompass the range of typical time steps reported in the literature for a wide range of force fields. It is expected that time steps as large as 0.4 fs result in faster simulation times, but may cause divergent results. A time step as small as 0.025 fs is expected to take approximately 16x more cpu-hours, but will produce accurate simulations. It is expected that there is a critical time step between 0.4 fs and 0.025 fs where further decreases in time step size do not change the simulation results.

A three-dimensionally periodic MD simulation box was constructed for each feedstock molecule, parameter set, temperature, and time step combination. Each molecular simulation consisted of 90.0 angstrom sides with the initial molecules added into it until the total number of carbon atoms in the system reached 900, resulting in a total density of 0.02455 g/cm³ for the pure carbon systems and 0.02663 g/cm³ for the hydrocarbon systems. Each system's initial state was equilibrated by running a NVT simulation of the system for 3 ns at the desired temperature with a fixed-topology force field with bond lengths similar to those of ReaxFF and with only the repulsive portion of the van der Waals term included. This step prevented the initial state from including high-energy coordinates such as overlapping atoms. The trajectories of the atoms were saved at 1 ns, 2 ns, and 3 ns; which were then used to establish three different simulation samples for each time step, temperature, parameter set and initial molecule combination, resulting in a total of 540 MD models. The fixed topology force field was then disabled and ReaxFF was enabled. Subsequently, the system energies were minimized and the simulations were run for 0.5 ns, 1.0 ns, or 1.5 ns; whichever time interval was required for the reaction to complete. The system energies were recorded at regular intervals throughout each ReaxFF-enabled simulation. An example of an equilibrated system is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3 Equilibrated system of C_2 molecules at 300K

4 Results and Discussion

An example of the influence of time step size on the simulated evolution of the reactive carbon gases is shown in Figure 4. It is clear in this figure that there is a maximum time step size in which the potential energy curves show close agreement (0.1 fs). For larger time step sizes, the corresponding potential energy curves diverge from these results. It is also clear from this figure that different simulation samples for a given set of parameters shows close agreement. For each combination of temperatures and feedstock molecules the corresponding maximum time step sizes are listed in Tables 1 and 2 for the Chenoweth and Nielson parameter sets, respectively.

Fig. 4 Influence of time step on potential energies for a system of C_4 initial gas molecules at 1,500K using the Chenoweth parameter set.

Table 1 Maximum time step size (in femtoseconds) for various reactive carbon gases at different temperatures using the Chenoweth parameter set

Molecule	300K	1,500K	3,000K
C	0.1	0.1	0.1
C_2	0.1	0.1	0.1
C_4	0.1	0.1	0.1
CH	0.2	0.1	0.1
C_2H_2	0.2	0.2	0.1
C_4H_4	0.2	0.2	0.1

Table 2 Maximum time step size for various reactive carbon gases at different temperatures using the Nielson parameter set

Molecule	300K	1,500K	3,000K
C	0.1	0.1	0.05
C_2	0.1	0.1	0.05
C_4	0.1	0.1	0.05
CH	0.2	0.1	0.1
C_2H_2	0.2	0.1	0.1
C_4H_4	0.2	0.1	0.1

The data in Tables 1 and 2 indicates that for a majority of the simulated conditions, a time step of 0.1 fs was sufficiently small to yield favorable results. The data also indicates that as the simulation temperature increases, smaller time steps are generally necessary for convergent results. For MD models with increasing simulation temperatures, the amplitude of vibration of single bonds increases. Therefore, it is expected that a larger portion of the nonlinear energy gradient is sampled over the course of the simulation which can cause time step errors to be more pronounced.

The data in Tables 1 and 2 also indicates that, in general, the pure carbon systems require smaller time steps than the hydrocarbon systems possibly because the higher mass of the hydrocarbon systems could alter the natural vibrational frequencies of the molecules and decrease the translational velocities, thus changing the time step size necessary for accurate simulation.

Fig. 5 Influence of temperature on potential energies for an initial gas of C atoms using the Nielson parameter set

Figure 5 shows a typical response of simulation temperature on the evolution of carbon reactive gasses. The potential energy generally shows a more rapid approach to its equilibrium value for higher temperatures, indicating that the reaction rates increase with increasing temperature. Also, the results are precise based on the similar response of the three different simulation samples at each temperature. The same trends were observed for other initial gas molecules considered in this study. For the pure-carbon systems, the potential energies converged to -148 to -160 kcal/mol for the Chenoweth parameters and -160 to -180 kcal/mol with the Nielson parameters. For the hydrocarbon systems the potential energies converged to -108 to -120 kcal/mol using either parameter set. For all the pure carbon systems, the equilibrium structures are mostly long linear branched carbon molecules with a small number of stable cyclic C_3 molecules as shown in the top of Figure 6. The final structure of the hydrocarbon systems consisted primarily of short linear hydrocarbon molecules with hydrogen atoms terminating the ends of the carbon chains shown in the middle Figure 6. As discussed later some pure

carbon systems formed large graphitic structures under critical conditions shown in the bottom of Figure 6.

Fig. 6 Final structures for initial gas of carbon atoms at 3,000K with the Nielson parameter set on the top, an initial gas system of C_2H_2 at 3,000K with the Chenoweth parameter set in the middle, and an initial gas of C_4 at 3,000K with the Chenoweth parameter set on the bottom

Fig. 7 Influence of parameter set on potential energies for initial gas of C_2 and C_2H_2 molecules at 1,500K

Figure 7 shows the influence of the ReaxFF parameter set on the potential energies of an initially pure C_2 system and an initially pure C_2H_2 system, both at 1,500K. From the figure it is clear that for the C_2 system, the Nielson parameter set predicts faster reaction rates than the Chenoweth parameter set. Similar trends have been observed for the other pure carbon systems and the CH system at all temperatures. From Figure 7, it is also clear that for the initially pure C_2H_2 system, the predicted reaction rates for the two parameter sets are nearly identical. A similar trend was observed for the C_4H_4 system at all temperatures.

Fig. 8 Influence of initial gas molecules on potential energies using the Nielson parameter set at 300K

Figure 8 shows a typical example of the influence of the initial gas molecule on the reaction rates of the

molecular system. From the figure it is evident that the system that starts as single carbon atoms has the fastest initial reaction rate, which is likely due to the high potential energy of single carbon atoms relative to the other initial gases which can be seen in Figure 8 at a time of 0 ns. Because of the high initial potential energy, there is a significant driving force to react very quickly to form C_2 , C_3 , C_4 , and higher-order carbon structures. Also, since there are no bond vibrations for C, all of the kinetic energy in a single carbon atom is translational. As the single carbon atoms react to form higher-order carbon chains with more bonds, more of the translational potential energy is transformed into bond vibration potential energy. As the translational energy of the molecules decrease, the kinetic energy barriers to lower energy states become more difficult to overcome. It is also important to note that all of the pure carbon systems converge to a similar potential energy in the final state, regardless of the initial molecular type. The same observation can be made about the hydrocarbon systems. Therefore, the equilibrated system is not sensitive to the initial gas molecules.

Fig. 9 Phase transformation predicted in pure-carbon systems as indicated by a sudden decrease in the relative potential energy near 0.25 ns.

It is interesting to note that for the Chenoweth parameter set at 3,000K for all of the pure carbon systems, a phase transformation was observed at around 0.25 ns, as shown in Figure 9. This transformation is characterized by the formation of large graphitic particles, instead of the long linear carbon chains that the other simulation parameters

produced. It is expected that at the transition point a small ring forms which can act as a nucleation site for a larger graphitic structure. This finding is significant because it demonstrates the ability of the ReaxFF to predict the formation of similar carbon structures; such as graphite, buckyballs, and carbon nanotubes; with specific simulation parameters. Similar observations have been made using *ab initio* simulations [27, 28].

5 Conclusions

The results in this study indicate that simulations of carbon-based reactive gasses using the ReaxFF are highly sensitive to the simulation parameters. In particular, it is clear that for pure carbon and hydrocarbon gasses simulated at 3,000 K a time step of 0.05 fs should be used, whereas for lower temperatures such as 300 K and 1,500 K, time steps of 0.1 fs are sufficient for accurate simulation. The results also indicate that the selection of parameter set may also have a significant influence on the simulation results. While the Nielson and Chenoweth parameter sets predict similar equilibrated potential energies, the reaction rates for the Nielson set are faster than those for the Chenoweth set for the pure-carbon systems. Although the Nielson and Chenoweth parameter sets usually result in simulations that predict the same equilibrated structures, it was observed that for pure-carbon systems simulated at 3,000 K, the Chenoweth parameter set yielded the formation large graphitic structures that the Nielson parameter set did not. This may indicate that the Chenoweth parameter set may be more appropriate for MD simulations in which the growth of graphitic structures is investigated.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by NASA under the Revolutionary Technology Challenges Program (Grant NNX09AM50A).

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